

SCALEDDEM

Scaling Democratic Innovations: Emerging Practices for Future Policies (Annex)/D1.2

WP 1, T 1.3

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1. First QCA Results

1.1. Preliminary QCA (61 Cordis projects = N cases)

The Qualitative Comparative Analysis was performed on 61 EU-funded project cases from the ScaleDem Knowledge Map. The raw dataset, as well as the calibrated dataset and the R Script, can be found in the folder for the cross-referencing of the results.

1.2. Operationalization and Skewness Check

Overall, the operationalization of the conditions and the template has produced consistent and interpretable results. The only minor issue is that the skewness check indicates a moderate imbalance of negative HIGH cases (where HIGH is absent) and positive IN cases (where IN is present). This might need to be addressed during the full-on implementation of the QCA and, if necessary, stressed in the paper as a potential research design limitation.

The outputs of the skewness checks are as follows:

- [1] "Set SUCCESS - Cases > 0.5 / Total number of cases: 26 / 61 = 42.62 %"
- [2] "Set OUT - Cases > 0.5 / Total number of cases: 27 / 61 = 44.26 %"
- **[3] "Set HIGH - Cases > 0.5 / Total number of cases: 17 / 61 = 27.87 %"**
- [4] "Set DEEP - Cases > 0.5 / Total number of cases: 26 / 61 = 42.62 %"
- **[5] "Set IN - Cases > 0.5 / Total number of cases: 41 / 61 = 67.21 %"**

1.3. Analysis of Necessity and Sufficiency

The analysis of the necessity for the presence of the outcome has yielded no result. No single condition (or combination of the two) has been found necessary for the outcome, in line with the standard methodological requirement of at least a 0.9 inclusion cut (Schneider and Wagemann, 2012; Oana and Schneider, 2021; see reference list in main text).

Table 1. *The Produced Conservative Solution*

	inclS	PRI	covS	covU	Cases
OUT*HIGH*IN	0.912	0.631	0.491	0.028	CIMULACT, CIVITAS ReVeAL; DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS, iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, WeGovNow
OUT*DEEP*IN	0.925	0.695	0.572	0.109	CCINDLE, Co-Inform, CO-SUSTAIN, CRITICAL CHANGLAB, DO, ENLIGHTENMe, INVOLVE, MultiPoD; DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS,

iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX,
REAL DEAL, WeGovNow

Solution	0.900	0.643	0.600		
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Note. See 1.6 for the glossary of the technical terms used in the table.

The analysis of sufficiency, on the other hand, has produced the QCA solution presented in Table 1 above. The conservative solution has been chosen due to its interpretability and prioritization of the empirical evidence (over the assumptions about the counterfactuals). No intermediate solution was produced as we had no directional expectations regarding the conditions' associations with the outcome. The conservative solution presented in Table 1 essentially indicates two different pathways, in both of which the interaction between “scaling out” and “scaling in” is observable. However, the third interacting condition differs in those pathways – it is either “scaling high” or “scaling deep”. Alternatively, the results of the sufficiency analysis are depicted in a simplified Venn diagram in Figure 1 in the main text.

The conservative solution has been developed with a 0.8 inclusion cut and a 0.7 PRI cut to ensure the robustness of the results. For further robustness checks, the solution also passed a stricter 0,85 inclusion test. Overall, the produced conservative solution offers only 0.600 coverage of cases, which will likely be expanded with further work on the dataset. Enhanced standard analysis procedures have been applied to the developed solution.

A sufficiency plot depicted in Figure 2 in the main text offers some insights into both the selection of typical cases for the theorization and analysis of relevant causal mechanisms as well as for the future improvement of the QCA through the analysis of the deviant consistency cases. The examples of positive typical, for instance, ENLIGHTENMe, DO, REAL DEAL. For the inferential purpose, these should be coupled with individually irrelevant cases from quadrant III. Mathematical calculations for the pairing of cases can be performed in line with Schneider (2024) for set-theoretic multi-methods research (SMMR). On the other hand, the analysis of cases such as iDem, CO-SUSTAIN, and WeGovNow would allow us to potentially pinpoint the missing explanatory conditions that could be relevant for the outcome.

Finally, a brief note has to be mentioned regarding the analysis of necessity for the absence of Y. While no single condition satisfies the necessity threshold, quite a few of the logical OR combinations do so, as can be seen in Table 2. The open question, however, in line with the QCA methodological literature, is whether these pathways represent something conceptually meaningful, e.g., a higher-order construct. Particularly, the combinations of $\sim\text{OUT} + \sim\text{DEEP}$; $\sim\text{OUT} + \sim\text{IN}$; $\sim\text{HIGH} + \sim\text{DEEP}$; $\sim\text{HIGH} + \sim\text{IN}$ could be meaningfully explored since they represent the absence of scaling dimensions. In line with the SMMR calculations (Schneider, 2024), the proposed typical cases for examining the possible meaningfulness of these pathways are KT4D for $\sim\text{OUT} + \sim\text{DEEP}$ and DEMOS-ACT for all four cases. The analysis of the necessity for the absence of the outcome, however, should be revisited with a larger number of cases.

Table 2. *The Necessity Pathways for the Absence of Y*

#	Pathways	inclN	RoN	covN (coverage)
1	OUT + ~HIGH	0.958	0.558	0.708
2	~OUT + ~DEEP	0.946	0.610	0.728
3	~OUT + DEEP	0.973	0.529	0.702
4	OUT + ~DEEP	0.942	0.613	0.728
5	~OUT + ~IN	0.909	0.660	0.739
6	~HIGH + ~DEEP	0.947	0.588	0.718
7	~HIGH + DEEP	0.959	0.584	0.720
8	HIGH + ~DEEP	0.925	0.632	0.730
9	~HIGH + ~IN	0.904	0.669	0.742

Additionally, typical cases can be explored for the individual conjuncts to see how potentially meaningful the generated pathways are. Nonetheless, given the small number of cases, these results should be treated with caution and should be double-checked once the QCA is finalized. However, bearing in mind the generated pathways and seeing whether they matter at the within-case level is essential during the qualitative case study stage.

Table 3. *Truth Table for the Presence of Y*

	OUT	HIGH	DEEP	IN	n	incl	PRI	cases
12	1	0	1	1	8	0.970	0.807	CCINDLE, Co-Inform, CO-SUSTAIN, CRITICAL CHANGELAB, DO, ENLIGHTENMe, INVOLVE, MultiPoD
14	1	1	0	1	2	0.965	0.704	CIMULACT, CIVITAS ReVeAL
16	1	1	1	1	10	0.944	0.710	DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS, iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, WeGovNow
13	0	1	0	0	1	0.963	0.605	WYDE
8	0	1	1	1	1	0.961	0.654	ACCTing
10	0	0	0	1	5	0.953	0.675	CMCG, INCITE-DEM, Itinerant Citizen Assembly of Bogotáj, PERITIA, PLEDGE
15	0	1	1	0	1	0.950	0.422	ISEED
6	0	1	0	1	2	0.936	0.530	COGOV, EUCOMMEET
3	0	0	1	0	1	0.917	0.243	D-CENT
4	0	0	1	1	5	0.903	0.411	ActEU, AECED, GenderQuotas, ITHACA, SMIDGE
2	0	0	0	1	8	0.820	0.269	CO3, EFORTT, ENCODE, EU3D, IDEal reSCUE, NEW_DEMOCRACY, PACITA, TITAN
1	0	0	0	0	17	0.643	0.072	CIT-PART, CIVICS, Co-VAL, DEMOS-ACT, DII, ECePS, IMPACT, KT4D, LIDD, LINKAGE, MEDIADELCOM, REBALANCE, RECONNECT, REDIRECT, SCALABLE DEMOCRACY, SEEVS, TROPICO

5	?	1	0	0	0			
7	?	1	1	0	0			
9	?	0	0	0	0			
11	?	0	1	0	0			

Table 4. Top 5 typical cases for the necessity pathways for the absence of Y

Table 4A: ~OUT+~DEEP					
Case	NecCond	Outcome	UniqCov	Best	MostTyp
DEMOS-ACT	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
KT4D	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
GenderQuotas	0.800	0.785	TRUE	0.230	FALSE
IDEal reSCUE	0.800	0.752	TRUE	0.296	FALSE
DII	1.000	0.835	TRUE	0.330	FALSE

Table 4B: ~OUT+~IN					
Case	NecCond	Outcome	UniqCov	Best	MostTyp
DEMOS-ACT	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
GenderQuotas	0.800	0.785	TRUE	0.230	FALSE
REBALANCE	1.000	0.855	TRUE	0.290	FALSE
IDEal reSCUE	0.800	0.752	TRUE	0.296	FALSE
DII	1.000	0.835	TRUE	0.330	FALSE

Table C: ~HIGH+~DEEP					
Case	NecCond	Outcome	UniqCov	Best	MostTyp
DEMOS-ACT	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
KT4D	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
IMPACT	0.837	0.835	TRUE	0.167	FALSE
LINKAGE	0.885	0.835	TRUE	0.215	FALSE
REBALANCE	0.969	0.855	TRUE	0.259	FALSE

Table D: ~HIGH+~IN					
Case	NecCond	Outcome	UniqCov	Best	MostTyp
DEMOS-ACT	1.000	0.918	TRUE	0.164	TRUE
IMPACT	0.837	0.835	TRUE	0.167	FALSE
REBALANCE	1.000	0.855	TRUE	0.290	FALSE
DII	1.000	0.835	TRUE	0.330	FALSE
LIDD	0.878	0.752	TRUE	0.374	FALSE

1.4. Cluster Diagnostics

The cluster diagnostics of scope conditions demonstrated a relatively high level of consistency of the sufficiency solution across geographical, family, and governance level clusters. The only visible

deviation in consistency was discovered in the Southern Europe cluster, suggesting that in the subsequent research, we should potentially be on the lookout for additional explanatory conditions (X). Moreover, the “Multinational or compared national” (11) and “National or subnational” (10) cases demonstrated a slightly lower level of consistency compared to the “Transnational or translocal” (31) and “EU multilevel” (9) cases. However, the difference was not as large as compared to the regional cluster. The details of the cluster diagnostics for each of the scope conditions can be found in Table 5.

Table 5. *Consistency tables from cluster diagnostics*

Table 5A: Consistencies by Family		
	OUT*HIGH*IN	OUT*DEEP*IN
Pooled	0.912	0.925
Between Administrative and/or electoral (6)	1.000	1.000
Between Direct and/or digital (25)	0.880	0.916
Between Participatory and/or deliberative (30)	0.930	0.929

Table 5B: Consistencies by Region		
	OUT*HIGH*IN	OUT*DEEP*IN
Pooled	0.912	0.925
Between Eastern Europe (2)	1.000	1.000
Between Northern Europe (27)	0.963	0.989
Between Southern Europe (10)	0.777	0.802
Between Western Europe (21)	0.965	0.936

Note. *Contains 1 NA.*

Table 5C: Consistencies by Level/Scope		
	OUT*HIGH*IN	OUT*DEEP*IN
Pooled	0.912	0.925
Between EU multilevel (9)	0.937	0.905
Between Multinational and compared national (11)	0.864	1.000
Between National or subnational (10)	0.826	0.872
Between Transnational or translocal (31)	0.937	0.943

1.5. Types of Cases

Table 6, based on the formal logic approach to sufficiency, helps us sort project cases into four groups based on two aspects: a) whether the project achieved the desired outcome (scaled successfully); b) whether the key success factors were present (the right combination of strategies and conditions).

Table 6. *Types of Cases*

1			1
Outcome present	II - Deviant case (coverage) (not relevant for tracing mechanisms)	I - Positive typical cases (most relevant for tracing mechanisms)	
Outcome not present	III - Irrelevant cases	IV - Deviant case (consistency) (relevant for mechanism-focused comparison)	
	0	Cause(s) and/or contextual conditions not present	Cause(s) and contextual conditions present

1.6. Glossary of technical terms used in the report

The following categorization is based on Schneider and Wagemann (2012).

- **inclS and inclN (Consistency for sufficiency / necessity):** Expresses the percentage of cases' set-membership scores in two sets that is in line with the statement that one of the two sets is a subset (or superset) of the other. It thus indicates to what degree the empirical data are in line with a postulated subset relation.
- **PRI (Proportional Reduction in Inconsistency):** Expresses how much it helps to know that a given condition X is a subset of outcome Y rather than a subset of either Y, its complement $\sim Y$, or the intersection between Y and $\sim Y$. PRI of 0.7 is recommended.
- **covS and covN (Coverage of sufficiency / necessity):** Assesses the relation in size between the condition set and the outcome set. Coverage sufficiency expresses how much of the outcome is covered by the sufficient condition. "Coverage" necessity is better understood in terms of the relevance and trivialness of a necessary condition.
- **covU (Unique coverage of the solution):** Percentage of all cases' set membership in the outcome uniquely covered by a single path of an equifinal solution term.
- **RoN (Relevance of Necessity):** Measures how far a set X is not only a superset of Y (and thus denotes a necessary condition), but also to what degree it is not much bigger than Y nor $\sim X$. If X is a superset of Y but much bigger than either Y, or $\sim X$, or both, then X is not a relevant, but a trivial necessary condition for Y.